

Influence Lifestyle and Price Impact on Trust: The Role of Mediation

Golan Hasan¹, Amelia Jeny Pratama², Nahrudien Akbar M³

^{1,2}Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Internasional Batam, Indonesia

³Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Pancasila Jakarta, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 25 September 2025	Lifestyle and price play an important role in increasing building trust and encouraging purchase decisions. This study aims to determine the relationship between lifestyle and price on purchase decisions mediated by brand awareness and trust. This study uses a quantitative method with a purposive sampling technique, data collection is carried out by distributing Google forms to 390 respondents with the criteria of having shopped at Tiktok Shop or Instagram Shop and domiciled in Batam City. In processing the data, researchers used SmartPLS 4 version 4.1.0.9. The results of the study showed that lifestyle price, and trust had a significant effect on purchase decisions. Lifestyle had a significant effect on purchase decisions mediated by trust. Price had a significant effect on purchase decisions mediated by trust. Lifestyle did not have a significant effect on purchase decisions mediated by trust.
Corresponding Author: Golan Hasan	
KEYWORDS: Lifestyle, Price, Trust, Purchase Decisions	

I. INTRODUCTION

Lifestyle has become one of a person's choices. According to Taino et al (2021) lifestyle has become a person's perspective. Currently, the younger generation dominates the use of Tiktok Shop and Instagram Shop, which makes them choose products based on their lifestyle. Usually, Tiktokshop and Instagram Shop use algorithms that can see products that suit their lifestyle through videos that someone likes.

Product pricing greatly influences a person's purchasing decision. Usually, entrepreneurs who sell in online stores will often offer cheaper prices compared to offline stores. According to Afriza et al (2024) price indicates the quality of the goods or services to be used. Currently, entrepreneurs are competing tightly, many strategies are used such as flash sales and bundling. This strategy has proven effective in increasing sales and making consumers aware of the brand.

When consumers trust the products sold, they have the potential to make transactions on that brand. If the media and sellers are trustworthy, consumers will not think twice about buying products from that brand. According to Usman et al (2020) trust will increase consumer expectations regarding products that have been paid for with the view of whether the product is in accordance with the price or not. Reputation can be built by creating trust in many ways. Trust is important, but trust needs to be balanced with guarantees. The refund

feature can make consumers confident in using the platform as an intermediary in transactions.

Previous research conducted by Brown et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of brand awareness and trust, but did not specifically link them to purchasing decisions. The TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop platforms have unique characteristics in terms of consumer interaction patterns and shopping experiences. Another novelty lies in the location of the study, namely in Batam City. As one of the rapidly growing cities with a young generation population that is active in using social media, Batam City provides a unique context for this study. Previously, there had been no study that specifically analyzed the influence of viral marketing, lifestyle, price, brand awareness, and trust on purchasing decisions on TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop.

This study has several important gaps that form the basis of the novelty in this study. Based on previous research conducted by Smith et al. (2021) has explored the influence of viral marketing, lifestyle, and price on consumer behavior, but has not specifically integrated these variables in the context of the latest government regulations governing social media-based e-commerce such as TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop. The first novel aspect of this study is its focus on the influence of current policies, such as price transparency requirements, advertising supervision, and consumer protection, which have not been widely discussed in previous literature. In addition, this study also involves the

role of brand awareness and trust as mediating variables in the relationship between viral marketing, lifestyle, price, and purchasing decisions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Lifestyle shows a person's way of life with a different perspective on life for each person (Akkaya, 2021). Lifestyle has a big impact on a person's purchasing decisions because it is related to their needs in using goods and services (Tirtayasa et al., 2023). According to Meistoh et al (2022) a person will group lifestyles based on aspects of life, such as desires and thoughts. By knowing a person's lifestyle, companies can group them as target markets to be targeted so that they can develop effective strategies (Matharu et al., 2021). The development of technology can support a person's lifestyle so that companies continue to innovate by following consumer lifestyles (Viorentina et al., 2023).

Price is one of the considerations for someone when buying a product because consumers compare price with the quality obtained (Rivai et al., 2021). According to Tecolalu et al (2021) pricing is not only about numbers but can shape consumers' views on a product or service (Benhardy et al., 2020). The application of a pricing strategy can increase a person's interest in the product (Sundah et al., 2022). Usually before consumers make a purchase they will compare prices in various places and the benefits obtained from the product (Wilistyorini et al., 2022). The use of discounts can affect consumers' views on the product, if it is too big it will be viewed negatively and if it is too small it will not be attractive (Abdullah et al., 2023).

Trust built using social media with a long-term strategy is one of the things that entrepreneurs must do (Bukhari et al., 2020). Someone can trust a product based on experience, the quality provided and transparent information about the product (Purwanto et al., 2024). According to Nur et al (2021) that trust has three main components, namely integrity, competence and good intentions. Purchasing through e-commerce is a form of someone's trust because they cannot check the product directly (Firdaus et al., 2024). Trust can be useful in every situation so entrepreneurs need to ensure building long term relationships with consumers to increase loyalty (Broto et al., 2024). It is important for entrepreneurs to determine the price they want to set in order to remain competitive in the market without reducing the value of the product (Hasan et al., 2022).

In making purchasing decisions, consumers always compare prices, quality and trusted brands (Viorentina et al., 2023). According to Wilistyorini et al (2022) there are 3 stages in purchasing decisions, namely, attitude, awareness and purchase intention. Purchasing decisions are not always influenced by internal conditions but can be influenced by external conditions such as discounts (Stefanny et al., 2022). Before someone decides to buy an item, they usually compare many things before deciding which one to choose (Hanaysha,

2022). Entrepreneurs need to innovate in creating marketing strategies so that consumers prefer the products being marketed (Dewi et al., 2022).

The Influence of Lifestyle on Trust

A person's lifestyle can influence their trust in a brand, if the brand chosen suits their lifestyle (Hanaysha, 2022). Brands that can adapt to consumers' lifestyles can be more easily trusted by consumers (Matharu et al., 2021). According to Agesti et al (2021) consumers trust brands that suit their lifestyles more. Trust in a brand can grow by adapting to consumers' lifestyles so that they trust the brand (Watanabe et al., 2020). Therefore, a person's lifestyle is one way to create Trust (Bukhari et al., 2020).

H1: Lifestyle has a significant effect on Trust

The Effect of Price on Trust

Price can increase trust in a brand by providing a price that is considered fair and in accordance with the quality (Park et al., 2021). Transparent prices often make brands more trusted by consumers because they are considered honest (Wilistyorini et al., 2022). According to Benhardy et al (2020) consumers trust products that have quality that matches the price more. Using strategies such as giving discounts and setting fixed prices can make consumers trust the product (Dewi et al., 2022). Therefore, a price that matches the quality can maintain consumer trust (Sundah et al., 2022).

H2: Price has a significant effect on Trust

The Influence of Trust on Purchase Decision

Trust can have an impact on purchase decisions if the brand always provides honest explanations about its products (Hasan et al., 2022). When consumers trust a brand, they will buy the product more often because they feel confident in the quality provided (Kristina et al., 2020). According to Stefanny et al (2022) when consumers trust a brand, it can reduce their risk in choosing a product. High consumer trust will make them make repeat purchase (Handerson et al., 2023). Therefore, trust is a top priority for entrepreneurs so that consumers can easily make purchase decisions (Sanggamele et al., 2022).

H3: Trust has a significant effect on Purchase Decision

Lifestyle Influence on Purchase Decision

Lifestyle has an impact on purchasing decisions if entrepreneurs follow the lifestyle of their consumers (Viorentina et al., 2023). Lifestyle can be seen based on their desires and views on something that is consumed. A person will choose a product that suits their lifestyle (Nurfajrina et al., 2021). Changes in trends and the development of technology can change lifestyles because what someone sees can influence their views (Tahir et al., 2022). In addition, individuals with an active lifestyle are more likely to buy products that support their mobility and comfort (Matharu et al., 2021). Therefore, lifestyle segmentation is important in

developing a more effective marketing strategy (Nur *et al.*, 2021).

H4: Lifestyle has a significant effect on Purchase Decision

The Influence of Price on Purchase Decision

Price has an impact on purchase decisions if the price given by a brand has an impact on their view of the product (Dewi *et al.*, 2022). Giving a low price can reduce the view of the quality of the product, thus affecting their purchasing decision (Wilistyorini *et al.*, 2022). Consumers often compare prices before making a purchase (Yasri *et al.*, 2020). A person's view of the appropriate price can increase a person's intention regarding a purchasing decision (Firdaus *et al.*, 2024). Therefore, flexible prices can increase sensitivity in purchase decision (Sundah *et al.*, 2022).

H5: Price has a significant effect on Purchase Decision

The Influence of Lifestyle on Purchase Decision mediated by Trust

Lifestyle will have an impact on Purchase decision with trust mediation if consumers believe their lifestyle matches the products they need (Bukhari *et al.*, 2020). According to Watanabe *et al.* (2020) that a person's trust in their lifestyle can make them buy products that match what they want (Agesti *et al.*, 2021). Increasing consumer trust in brands that match their lifestyle will reduce the risk when using the product (Matharu *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, lifestyle can develop if consumers trust brands that match their views which leads to increased purchase decisions (Hanaysha, 2022).

H6: Lifestyle has a significant effect on Purchase Decision mediated by Trust

III. METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach to analyze the influence of viral marketing, lifestyle, and price on purchase decisions, with brand awareness and trust as mediating variables. This approach was chosen because it allows for accurate measurement, so that it can provide a deeper understanding of the factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions on TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop. To obtain relevant data, this study uses a survey method by distributing questionnaires online to consumers who have shopped through TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop in Batam City. Batam City was chosen as the research location because it has a large population and a high level of digital users, especially among the younger generation who are the main targets of the TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop platforms.

The population in this study consists of consumers who have purchased or are interested in using TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop in Batam City. The selection of this population is based on the increasing trend of Batam City society towards TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop. Batam City was chosen as the research location because of the rapid growth in digital trading activities and continues to grow, which makes the Batam City environment very relevant to

analyzing consumer behavior on TikTok Shop and Instagram Shop. The respondents involved are individuals who have made transactions through Tiktok Shop or Instagram Shop, thus ensuring that respondents have real experiences that are in accordance with the objectives of this study.

This study applies a non-probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling approach. Sample selection is based on certain criteria, namely consumers who have experience in using Tiktokshop and Instagram Shop. In addition, the respondents selected are also based on the influence of viral marketing, lifestyle and price factors that play a role in their purchasing decisions. The purposive sampling method is used to ensure that the samples obtained are in accordance with the objectives of the study, namely analyzing purchase decisions (Hair *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the samples obtained are expected to provide accurate data on the topic being studied.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

In this study, data collection used a questionnaire, which was successfully collected from 390 respondents with various characteristics such as gender, age, employment status, how often they shop online, monthly income, spending when shopping at Tiktok Shop / Instagram Shop and what factors influence shopping at Tiktok Shop / Instagram Shop. The results of the respondent demographic analysis are presented in the following table:

Based on the data presented, most respondents in this survey were female, 219 people (56.2%), while males numbered 171 people (43.8%). In terms of age, the largest group was in the range of 17-24 years (41.5%), followed by 25-32 years (32.1%), 33-40 years (20.3%), and the smallest was the 41 – 46 years group (6.2%). This shows that the majority of respondents are young people, who are likely to be more active in online shopping. In terms of employment status, the majority of respondents were students (37.4%), followed by self-employed (27.4%), private employees (19.2%), civil servants (10.7%), and the smallest were housewives (4.6%). This shows that most respondents are still in education or work independently. Regarding the frequency of online shopping on TikTok Shop or Instagram Shop, most respondents shop 1-2 times a month (28.5%), followed by once every 3 months (22.1%), 3-4 times a month (18.8%), every day (17.2%), and 1-2 times a week (13.4%). This indicates that even though this platform is popular, most respondents still shop infrequently.

In terms of monthly income, the largest group has an income of IDR 6,000,000 - IDR 9,000,000 (38.7%), followed by IDR 4,000,000 - IDR 5,500,000 (31.3%), more than IDR 9,000,000 (22.6%), and the least is IDR 2,500,000 - IDR 3,500,000 (7.4%). Meanwhile, in terms of spending when shopping at TikTok Shop or Instagram Shop, the majority of respondents spent IDR 100,000 – IDR 350,000 (74.6%),

while 25.4% of respondents spent more than IDR 350,000. As for the factors that influence the decision to shop at TikTok Shop or Instagram Shop, the number of promos & discounts (37.2%) is the main factor, followed by low prices (33.8%), and ease of shopping from anywhere (28.7%). Uniquely, no respondents chose the "need" factor as their main reason for shopping, indicating that purchasing decisions are more influenced by external factors such as price and promotions than urgent needs.

Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results of the hypothesis test analysis using PLS-SEM, various relationships between the variables studied were obtained. The level of significance is based on the T-statistics value ≥ 1.96 and P-values ≤ 0.05 .

The test results on LS against T are also significant with T-statistics of 2.288 and 1.983 respectively, and P-values of 0.022 and 0.047, P against T, the T-statistic values of 2.766 and 4.209 and P-values of 0.006 and 0.000 indicate that it is significant. Furthermore, B T against PD show an influence with T-statistics of 7.497 and 5.463 and a P-value of 0.000, meaning that the higher T, the greater the influence on PD. LS against PD and P against PD, with T-statistic 2.336 and 3.740, and P-value 0.020 and 0.000, indicating that LS and P have a significant effect on PD. Overall, the results confirm that all relationships between variables in the research model are significant.

The results of the Indirect Effect test show that The same thing happens to P on PD mediated by T with a T-statistic of 3.560 and a P-value of 0.000, indicating that it is significant. Overall, five of the six mediation relationships in this model are significant, except for Hypothesis 15 which indicates that T is not an effective mediator in the relationship between LS and PD.

R-square test

The results of the analysis indicate the extent to which the independent variables are able to explain the dependent variables in the research model. The R-square value indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables, while the adjusted R-square is a version that has been adjusted to consider the number of predictors in the model, so that it is more accurate in measuring the predictive ability of the model. R Square > 0.70 is considered strong, > 0.50 is considered moderate and > 0.25 is considered weak.

In this result, the BA variable has an R^2 value of 0.548, which means that 54.8% of the variance in BA can be explained by its independent variables, while PD has an R^2 of 0.80, indicating that 58% of the variance in PD can be explained by the constructs that influence it. Meanwhile, T has an R^2 value of 0.536, which means that 53.6% of the variance in T can be explained by its independent variables. The small difference between R^2 and R^2 adjusted indicates that the model used is quite stable and does not experience significant overfitting. Thus, it can be concluded that the independent variables in

this study have a fairly strong influence in explaining the dependent variables analyzed.

Discussion

Positive Influence of Lifestyle on Trust

The Lifestyle hypothesis is proven to have a direct influence on Trust with a t-statistic value of 2.303 and p-values of 0.021, indicating that the suitability of the product to the consumer's lifestyle can increase their trust in the brand. When a brand is able to understand and reflect the values and habits of its consumers, consumers will feel more connected and trust the brand. These results are also supported by Watanabe et al (2020) who said that the relationship between products and consumer lifestyles can create a positive perception of the brand, thereby increasing customer trust.

Positive Influence of Price on Trust

The Price hypothesis is proven to have a direct influence on Trust with a t-statistic value of 3.175 and p-values of 0.002, indicating that transparent and competitive prices can increase customer trust. Consumers tend to trust brands that offer prices that match product quality and have no hidden costs. These results are also supported by Benhardy et al (2020) who said that price transparency and the suitability between price and product quality can strengthen consumer trust in a brand.

Positive Influence of Trust on Purchase Decision

The Trust Hypothesis is proven to have a direct influence on Purchase Decision with a t-statistic value of 2.423 and p-values of 0.015, indicating that the higher consumer trust in a brand, the more likely they are to make a purchase. Consumers who have a high level of trust in a brand are more likely to buy its products. Factors such as transparency of information, positive reviews, and product quality assurance are important factors in building trust that drives purchasing decisions. These results are also supported by Dewi et al (2022) who said that consumer trust in a brand plays an important role in reducing uncertainty and increasing their confidence in making purchases.

Positive Influence of Lifestyle on Purchase Decision

The Lifestyle Hypothesis is proven to have a direct influence on Purchase Decision with a t-statistic value of 5.310 and p-values of 0.000, indicating that the suitability of the product to the consumer's lifestyle can influence purchasing decisions. Products that are relevant to consumer habits and preferences have a higher appeal than products that do not match their lifestyle trends. These results are also supported by Agesti et al (2021) who said that products that match consumers' lifestyles tend to be more easily accepted and in demand, because consumers feel that the product can support the activities and values they adhere to.

Positive Influence of Price on Purchase Decision

The Price hypothesis is proven to have a direct influence on Purchase Decision with a t-statistic value of 3.930 and p-

values of 0.000, indicating that prices that are considered appropriate to product quality will increase purchasing interest, while prices that are too high or not comparable to the benefits offered can reduce the appeal of the product. Competitive and transparent prices play an important role in encouraging consumers to buy products, especially in e-commerce which relies heavily on price comparisons and promotions. These results are also supported by Dewi et al (2022) who said that competitive prices and in accordance with consumer expectations can improve product perception, thereby encouraging purchasing decisions.

Positive Influence of Lifestyle on Purchase Decisions Mediated by Trust

The Lifestyle Hypothesis is proven to have no direct influence on Purchase Decision mediated by trust with a t-statistic value of 1.667 and p-values of 0.096 indicating that product suitability with consumer lifestyle does not significantly increase purchasing decisions through trust. Although a product can reflect a certain lifestyle, it does not always make consumers automatically trust the brand. These results are also supported by Faradila et al (2025) who said that consumer trust is more influenced by factors such as product quality, customer reviews, and brand reputation than simply the suitability of the product to their lifestyle.

IV. CONCLUSION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that viral marketing, lifestyle, and price have a significant influence on purchasing decisions, with brand awareness and trust acting as mediating variables in Tiktok Shop and Instagram Shop. There are two insignificant hypotheses, namely the influence of viral marketing and lifestyle on purchase decisions mediated by trust. In increasing consumer purchasing decisions, entrepreneurs need to focus more on creating marketing that has the potential to go viral, analyzing consumer lifestyles and paying attention to product pricing.

With the end of this research, the researcher felt that he had experienced limitations during the research. First, the limited manpower, time and ability of the researcher in conducting the research. Second, the questionnaire questions were often misunderstood by someone which caused the data not to be distributed perfectly. Third, there was dishonesty of the respondents in filling out the questionnaires given so that it had an impact on the quality of the data produced.

Suggestions

Based on the research results, there are several suggestions that researchers provide for further researchers. First, add or replace variables to expand knowledge about variables that impact purchasing decisions. Second, use other cities with larger populations to obtain more accurate data. Third, if possible, increase the research location from city scale to national scale. Finally, look for questionnaires with

easier questions that are relevant to the conditions that occur. This is expected to make further research get perfect results.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullah, M. A. F., Febrian, W. D., Perkasa, D. H., Wuryandari, N. E. R., Pangaribuan, Y. H., & Fathuhani. (2023). The Effect of Brand Awareness, Price Perception and Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM) Toward Purchase Intention on Instagram. *Transdisciplinary Symposium on Business, Economics, and Communication*, 1(1), 689–698. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v8i12.13716>
2. Afriza, M., Alvarez, R., & Sadat, A. M. (2024). The Influence Of Viral Marketing, Brand Awareness, And Distribution Intensity On Purchase Decision Through Brand Preference In Mixue Consumers. *International Journal of Current Economics & Business Ventures*, 4(1), 205–217. <https://scholarsnetwork.org/journal/index.php/ijeb>
3. Agesti, N., Mohammad, ;, Ridwan, S., & Budiarti, E. (2021). The Effect of Viral Marketing, Online Customer Review, Price Perception, Trust on Purchase Decisions with Lifestyle as Intervening Variables in the Marketplace Shopee in Surabaya City. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(2), 496–507. <https://doi.org/dx.doi.org/10.18415/ijmmu.v8i3.2526>
4. Agus, N., Nugraha, S., Bagus, I., Putra, U., Made, I., & Amerta, S. (2023). The Role of Brand Awareness in the Influence of Instagram Advertising and Viral Marketing on Culinary Purchase Decisions. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies*, 3(2), 280–286. <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijssers/V03I2Y2023-08>,
5. Akkaya, M. (2021). Understanding the impacts of lifestyle segmentation & perceived value on brand purchase intention: An empirical study in different product categories. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 27(3), 100155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100155>
6. Amperawati, E. D., Rahmawati, Haerofiatna, & Rusmawan, T. (2024). Investigating the role of viral marketing, and brand awareness on purchase decisions: An empirical study in Indonesian online shops. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 8(3), 1715–1726. <https://doi.org/10.52677/j.ijdns.2024.2.016>
7. Anindya, F., & Indriastuti, H. (2023). The Rise of Viral Marketing and Brand Awareness Influence Purchase Decisions Of Somethinc Products. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAAR)*, 7(1), 173–183.

- <https://jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/IJEBAR>
8. Arifianti, S. A. P., & Untarini, N. (2023). The Influence of Brand Ambassadors, Viral Marketing, and Consumer Trust n-on Purchase Decisions (Study on MS Glow Skincare Product Consumers). *International Management Conference and Progressive Paper*, 1(1), 322–333.
 9. Benhardy, K. A., Hardiyansyah, Putranto, A., & Ronadi, M. (2020). Brand image and price perceptions impact on purchase intentions: Mediating brand trust. *Management Science Letters*, 10(14), 3425–3432. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.5.035>
 10. Broto, F. S. W. W., Karnalim, T., & Anastasia, M. (2024). The Influence of Viral Marketing and Brand Awareness on Consumer Purchase Intentions for Mixue Beverage Products in Malang. *International Journal of Business and Applied Economics*, 3(4), 749–766. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijbae.v3i4.10350>
 11. Bukhari, F., Hussain, S., Ahmed, R. R., Streimikiene, D., Soomro, R. H., & Channar, Z. A. (2020). Motives and role of religiosity towards consumer purchase behavior in western imported food products. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12010356>
 12. Clarissa, C., & Bernarto, I. (2022). The Influence of Brand Ambassador, Brand Awareness, Brand Image and Prices on Purchase Decisions on Online Marketplace. *Business and Entrepreneurial Review*, 22(2), 273–288. <https://doi.org/10.25105/ber.v22i2.14966>
 13. Dewi, B. S., Prayoga, Y., & Rambe, B. H. (2022). Influence of Product Quality, Promotion, Price, Trust On the Purchase Decision at Alfa Scorpii Rantauprapat. *Quantitative Economics and Management Studies*, 3(4), 571–578. <https://doi.org/10.35877/454ri.qems1025>
 14. Ekasari, R., & Jaya, I. M. L. (2021). The Determinants of Consumer Purchasing Decisions of Health Food Products : An Empirical Study from Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business Vol*, 8(12), 519–528. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no12.0519>
 15. Faradila, F., & Silitonga, P. (2025). Product Quality, Lifestyle and Social Media Marketing Increase Purchase Decision Through Brand Trust. *Journal of Management*, 18(1), 677–696.
 16. Fatah, M. Al, & Arsyad, M. J. (2022). The Effect Of Viral Marketing and Brand Image On Purchase Decisions Through E-Trust: (Study on Kahf Skincare Customers). *Economic and Business Journal*, 1(1), 9–16. <http://ecbis.net/index.php/go/article/view/2>
 17. Finthariasari, M. F., Ratnawili, R., & Halim, N. (2022). Purchasing Decisions: The Analysis Effect Of The Variables Life Style, Celebrity Endorser, And Brand Image. *EKOMBIS REVIEW: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 10(2), 661–672. <https://doi.org/10.37676/ekombis.v10i2.2224>
 18. Firdaus, R. A., Wulandari, D., & Utami, E. S. (2024). The Influence of Viral Marketing, Endorsments and Prices on Purchase Intention Through Brand Image on Wardah Cosmetics Consumers in the Horse Shoe Area, East Java. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 8(6), 349–354.
 19. Graciola, A. P., De Toni, D., Milan, G. S., & Eberle, L. (2020). Mediated-moderated effects: High and low store image, brand awareness, perceived value from mini and supermarkets retail stores. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 55(February), 102117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102117>
 20. Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R*.
 21. Hanaysha, J. R. (2022). Impact of social media marketing features on consumer’s purchase decision in the fast-food industry: Brand trust as a mediator. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 2(2), 100102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijime.2022.100102>
 22. Handerson, D. G., & Hartono, S. (2023). The Impact of Brand Image, Viral Marketing, and Consumer Trust on Purchase Decisions on Good Day RTD Products. *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, 7(2), 273–280.
 23. Hasan, G., & Elviana. (2022). Effect Of Brand Image, Celebrity Endorsement, EWOM, Brand Awareness And Social Media Communication On Purchase Intention With Brand Trust As A Mediation Variable On Smartphone Users In Batam City. *Conference on Business, Social Sciences and Technology*, 2(1), 153–161.
 24. Hasan, G., & Scorpianti, E. (2022). The influence of usefulness, entertainment, interaction, enjoyment, and familiarity to purchase music platform subscriptions in Millennials and Gen-z communities through trust mediation. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Pemasaran Jasa*, 15(2), 161–176. <https://doi.org/10.25105/jmpj.v15i2.14071>
 25. Kristina, T., & Sugiarto, C. (2020). The role of trust mediates in the influence of social media marketing and Electronic Word-of-Mouth on purchase intention. *Management and Entrepreneurship: Trends of Development*, 4(14), 102–113. <https://doi.org/10.26661/2522-1566/2020-4/14-08>

26. Liyanapathirana, Y. M. (2021). Viral Marketing and Impulse Buying with the Mediating Effect of Online Trust: During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Conference on Management and Economics, 1*(1), 411–426.
27. Matharu, M., Jain, R., & Kamboj, S. (2021). Understanding the impact of lifestyle on sustainable consumption behavior: a sharing economy perspective. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal, 32*(1), 20–40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-02-2020-0036>
28. Meistoh, S., & Hadita, H. (2022). Impact of Hedonic Lifestyle Through Brand Image on Interest of Gopay Users in Generation Z in Bekasi City. *Dinasti International Journal of Digital Business Management, 3*(5), 703–712. <https://doi.org/10.31933/dijdbm.v3i5.1340>
29. Mukherjee, S., Das, M. K., & Chakraborty, T. K. (2023). Viral Marketing in Increasing Brand Awareness and Predicting Purchase Intention: Exploring Mediating Role of Brand Loyalty in FMCG Sector. *Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management, 10*(04), 61–77. <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjebm.2023.v10i04.001>
30. Murni, D., & Salim, M. (2024). The The Mediating Role Of Trust In The Influence Of Viral Marketing And Online Consumer Reviews On Purchasing Decisions Skintific Product In TikTok. *EKOMBIS REVIEW: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Bisnis, 12*(1), 487–498. <https://doi.org/10.37676/ekombis.v12i1.4971>
31. Navaril, R. G., & Usman, D. O. (2020). Effect of Brand Awareness, Price, Product Quality Towards Decisions to Purchase Social Media Instagram. *SSRN, 1*(1), 1–21. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3637671
32. Nur, M. R. T., Fathoni, M. A., & Sari, L. P. (2021). The Impact of Awareness, Lifestyle and Halal Certification on The Buying Interests of MSME’s Halal Food Products in DKI Jakarta. *El-Barka: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, 4*(2), 156–189. <https://doi.org/10.21154/elbarka.v4i2.3207>
33. Nurfajrina, A., Handayani, T., & Sari, L. P. (2021). The Effect of Halal Awareness and Lifestyle on The Purchase Decision of Japanese Food in Jakarta. *Journal of Islamic Economics and Social Science (JIESS), 2*(2), 66. <https://doi.org/10.22441/jiess.2021.v2i2.001>
34. Park, C. W., Sutherland, I., & Lee, S. K. (2021). Effects of online reviews, trust, and picture-superiority on intention to purchase restaurant services. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management, 47*(8), 228–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2021.03.007>
35. Pasaribu, R. M., Tampubolon, F. Y., & Matodang, V. (2023). Trust Mediates Channel Integration And Viral Marketing In Repurchase Intention Golds Saving Products In PT Pegadaian Pringgagan Medan. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management, 11*(06), 4956–4966. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v11i06.em03>
36. Purwanto, A., & Praditya, R. (2024). The Role of Viral Marketing, Brand Image and Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions. *PROFESOR : Professional Education Studies and Operations Research, 1*(01), 11–15. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.7777/nr27d428>
37. Putri, A., & Ketut Rahyuda, I. (2023). Customer Trust as a Mediator of the Influence of Viral Marketing and Brand Image on Online Purchase Decisions on Scarlett Products in Denpasar City. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research, 07*(02), 8–15. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.7777/nr27d428>
38. Rivai, J., & Zulfitri. (2021). The Role of Purchasing Decisions Mediating Product Quality, Price Perception, and Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction of Kopi Janji Jiwa. *Journal of Business and Management Studies, 3*(2), 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.32996/jbms.2021.3.2.4>
39. Sanggamele, A. J., Massie, J. D. D., & Arie, F. V. (2022). The Influence of Viral Marketing and Customer Trust Toward Customer Purchase Intention of Xiaomi Smartphone in Manado Pengaruh Viral Marketing Dan Kepercayaan Pelanggan Terhadap Niat Membeli Customer Pada Smartphone Xiaomi Di Manado. *Jurnal EMBA, 10*(4), 883–892.
40. Stefanny, N., Rahmiati, F., & Roni, M. (2022). The role of brand image and brand trust in mediating the influence of e-WOM on purchase decision (case of video-on-demand Netflix). *IDEAS: Journal of Management & Technology, 2*(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.33021/ideas.v2i1.3696>
41. Sundah, F., Tecoalu, M., & Wahyoedi, S. (2022). The Effect of Trust, Price and Ease of Transaction on Buying Interest and Their Implications on Puchase Decisions Study PT. Indonesia Maybank Finance Online Customer. *International Journal of Social Science, Educational, Economics, Agriculture Research and Technology (IJSET), 2*(9), 431–442.
42. Tahir, F., Nisar, A., & Rehmat, M. (2022). Impact of Social Media Advertising on Purchase Intention: Mediation of Advertising Literacy, Influencer Review, E-Lifestyle and Brand Awareness Fizza Tahir 1 , Asma Nisar 2 , Maryam Rehmat 3. *Journal*

- of Policy Research*, 9(1), 409–424.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8070870>
43. Taino, R., Rodrigues Cardoso, R., & Luzzi Las Casas, A. (2021). Does Viral Marketing Create Brand Awareness? an Exploratory Study With University Students. *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability RISUS*, 12(03), 109–117.
<https://doi.org/10.23925/2179-3565.2021v12i3p109-117>
44. Tecoalu, M., Tj, H. W., & Ferdian, F. (2021). Effect of Price Perception and Brand Awareness on Service Quality Mediated By Purchasing Decisions. *Journal of Humanities, Social Science, Public Administration and Management (HUSOCPUMENT)*, 1(4), 183–195.
<https://doi.org/10.51715/husocpument.v1i4.127>
45. Tirtayasa, S., & Ramadhani, F. (2023). The Effect Of Price, Product Quality and Hedonism Lifestyle On Diamond Shops Purchasing Decisions Mediated By Perceived Value at Diamond Shops In Medan City. *Jurnal Ekonomi*, 12(02), 520–531.
46. Usman, O., & Zuhurifa, N. H. (2020). The Influence of Viral Marketing, Celebrity Endorse and Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention on Somethinc Cosmetic Products. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(1), 1–14.
47. Viorentina, D., & Santoso, S. (2023). Influence of Brand Image, Product Quality, and Lifestyle on Smartphone Purchase Decision in Indonesia. *Expert Journal of Marketing*, 11(1), 25–33.
48. Watanabe, E. A. de M., Alfinito, S., Curvelo, I. C. G., & Hamza, K. M. (2020). Perceived value, trust and purchase intention of organic food: a study with Brazilian consumers. *British Food Journal*, 122(4), 1070–1184. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-05-2019-0363>
49. Wilistyorini, V., & Sussanto, H. (2022). the Effect of Product Quality, Service Quality, Price, and Trust on Purchase Decisions (Case Study on Shopeefood Users). *International Journal Management and Economic*, 1(3), 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.56127/ijme.v1i3.279>
50. Yasri, Y., Susanto, P., Hoque, M. E., & Gusti, M. A. (2020). Price perception and price appearance on repurchase intention of Gen Y: do brand experience and brand preference mediate? *Heliyon*, 6(11), 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05532>